

Title:

Trends of demand satisfied by modern methods of contraceptive among women of reproductive age between 1990 and 2018 in Nigeria, using Demographic and Health Surveys: A synthetic cohort

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Executive summary

Background

The use of contraceptives, also known as family planning (FP), offers women the power to choose whether they want to have children or not, when to have children and how many they would want to have. FP is a human right, therefore, it is important to know the trend of the demand satisfied by modern contraceptive methods over women's reproductive lifespan. The United Nations' International Conference on Population and Development (ICPD) held in Cairo, in 1994 alongside the global FP 2030 goal and the Sustainable Developmental Goals 3.7 and 5.6 uphold the policies of FP to be rights-based. This approach would stimulate demand for modern FP and scale up the percentage of women whose demand is met. An understanding of the trend of the main indicators for modern FP is needed globally and across different regions of the world among Women of Reproductive Age (WRA) from the 1990s till date.

The proportion of all WRA using modern FP, called the modern Contraceptive Prevalence Rate or (**mCPR**) increased from 36% in 1990 to 44% in 2019 globally. Among the 1.9 billion WRA (15-49 years) worldwide in 2019, 1.1 billion have a **need for FP** and the percentage of **demand satisfied by modern methods** was 78%. Globally, from 1990 to 2010, **unmet need for FP** declined from 15.5% to 12.3%. The contraceptive **method mix** increasingly used between 1995 and 2015, varied between injectables and implants in Sub-Sahara Africa, Latin America and South East Asia while oral pills are becoming less used. The Nigerian government in 1988, set its first National Population Policy in motion, unofficially called "the four-child policy" which was revised in 2004 with the objectives of FP, health and education. This was followed by the "Free FP Commodity Policy" in 2010, the FP Blueprint in 2013 and then Nigeria's FP 2030 which aligned its goals with the Global FP 2030. However, the political will and financial commitments of the Nigerian government towards implementing policies have been inadequate.

Aim

The objective of this study is to analyze the changes over time of the indicators of modern FP in Nigeria. The five indicators of interest includes: **mCPR**, **need for FP**, **demand satisfied by modern methods**, **unmet need for FP** and **method mix**. I will use the findings to identify gaps and recommend strengthening of Sexual and Reproductive Health policies in Nigeria to address those gaps.

Methods

With a synthetic cohort approach, I used five Nigeria population-representative surveys from 1990-2018 to estimate several indicators of FP for women born between 1971 and 1975. For each of the five surveys, I assessed the socio-demographic characteristics of the 1971-75 cohort by level of education, marital status, parity, employment at the time of the survey, residence and religion. Afterwards, I analyzed the FP indicators and thus charted a synthetic birth cohort of women as they age over their reproductive life-span (from 15-19 at the time of 1990 survey to 43-47 years at the time of the 2018 survey), examining how these indicators change over time. The statistical analyses were done using Software R version 4. 1. 3.

Results

Greater than 60% of the women in the 1971-75 birth cohort were educated. Even though, women lived more in the rural residence all through their reproductive life from 15-19 till 43-47 years, women at ages older than 28-32 were mostly working at the time of the survey compared to women at their 15-19 years, as expected. Furthermore, the percentage of women who were married or cohabiting moved from 37% to 89% as women aged from when women were at their 15-19 years to when women were at their 28-32 years and above. Additionally, the mean number of children birthed at the end of women's reproductive life was 6 and their religion was equally distributed between Christianity and Islam. As the women grew older, the change in their mCPR, need for FP and demand satisfied by modern methods followed the same trend. These percentages increased as the women grew from when they were at their 15-19 years and peaked when they were at their 33-37 and 38-42 years. This corresponds with the findings from Yameen et al in Pakistan, who documented that women had higher odds to use FP when they are 35 years or younger compared to older than 35 years. The Nigerian policies (though not fully implemented) as well as the International Non-Government Organizations (INGOs), have contributed to the increase in mCPR and demand satisfied by modern methods over the years since these INGOs have been at the fore-front of several FP programs in Nigeria.

Conclusion

The demand satisfied by modern methods of contraceptives among WRA in Nigeria needs to be scaled up and this requires an increased political will towards empowering women on their sexual and reproductive health and rights at every reproductive year age-group.

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List of Abbreviations

AIDS:	Acquired Immunodeficiency Disease Syndrome
BMGF:	Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation
CHWS:	Community Health Workers.
DFID:	Department for International Development
DHS:	Demographic and Health Survey
DMPA-SC:	Depot-Medroxy Progesterone Acetate-Sub Cutaneous
FCT:	Federal Capital Territory
FG:	Federal Government
FgoN:	Federal Government of Nigeria
FmoH:	Federal Ministry of Health
FP:	Family Planning
GHSC-PSM:	Global Health Supply Chain Program-Procurement and Supply Management (USAID)
HIV:	Human Immunodeficiency Virus
ICPD:	International Conference on Population and Development
INGOs:	International Non-Governmental Organisations
IPPF:	International Planned Parenthood Federation
IUD:	Intra-uterine device.
LAM:	Lactational amenorrhoea
LARC:	Long-acting reversible contraceptive
LMICs:	Low- and Middle-Income Countries
MCPR:	Modern Contraceptive Prevalence Rate
MDG:	Millennial Developmental Goal
MNCH:	Maternal, Newborn and Child Health
NPP:	National Population Policy
PPFN:	Planned Parenthood Federation of Nigeria
SAM:	Short-acting method
SDG:	Sustainable Developmental Goal
SRH:	Sexual and Reproductive Health
SSA:	Sub-Sahara Africa
STI:	Sexually Transmitted Infections
TFR:	Total Fertility Rate

UK: United Kingdom
UN: United Nations
UNFPA: United Nations Population Fund
USAID: United States Agency for International Development
WHO: World Health Organization
WRA: Women of Reproductive Age

CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

The use of contraceptive also known as family planning (FP), offers women and couples the power to choose whether they want to have children or not, when to have children and how many they would want to have. Since women become pregnant, FP should be a strategy for women empowerment rather than a strategy for population control which it has been over the years (1). FP is a human right, therefore, it is important to know the trend of the demand satisfied by modern contraceptive methods over women's reproductive years. The current United Nation's SDG target 3.7 emphasizes a "universal access" to Sexual and Reproductive Health (SRH) services including FP by 2030 while SDG target 5.6 emphasizes "universal access" to SRH and reproductive rights (2). SRH includes maternal health and as Gutmacher lancet Commission highlights in their statement of purpose, "to advance health, we must advance rights" advancing women's reproductive right to voluntarily decide on childbearing impacts largely on maternal health. In 1987, the use of contraception was the first of the four pillars of the UN's Safe Motherhood Initiative launched to lower the maternal mortalities in LMICs by half in 2000 (2). Contraception use in these regions continue to get global strengthening by its inclusion in the UN's MDG.5 from 2000-2015 (3).

Globally, between 1990 and 2010, the prevalence of contraceptive use increased by approximately 16% and in a study done in 2008, among 172 countries worldwide, it was estimated that maternal deaths would have been 1.8 times higher without contraceptive use (4). Additionally, meeting the contraceptive needs of women globally would reduce maternal deaths by 35% and unsafe abortions by 64% (5). Regarding population control, between 1990 and 2019, total fertility rate (TFR) in the world declined from 3.2 to 2.5 live births per woman due to increased use of contraceptives. This reduction in Central and South Asia was 4.0 to 1.9 births per woman while in SSA (the part of the world with the highest fertility rate), it was from 6.3 to 4.6 live births per woman (6). Nigeria, being the most populous country in SSA is currently at 5.1 live births per woman declining from 6.5 live births per woman in 1990 (7). Other benefits of family planning includes: reduction of child mortality, prevention of Sexually-Transmitted Infections (STIs) including HIV/AIDs, economic growth within the country as a result of reduced fertility rate and its consequent moderate population size (8).

The United Nations' International Conference on Population and Development (ICPD) held in Cairo, in 1994 emphasized the use of FP to reduce fertility rate as well as embracing FP as a human right that should be safeguarded (9). However developing countries with high levels of female illiteracy makes

FP policies that are more focused on population decline rather than women empowerment. For example in SSA, about 75% of girls would get married before their 18th birthday while Nigeria, has the highest number of child brides (22 million) in SSA (10). In July 2012, FP 2020 was birthed following the London FP Summit hosted by UK Government and BMGF with an aspiring target to scale-up the use of modern FP out of free-will to 120 million additional women globally by 2020 (11). At the end of the year 2020, FP 2020 transitioned into FP 2030 with a revised target to be more committed to “equitable and rights-based approaches” among others (11).

Rights-based FP approaches entails designing and embarking on FP programs that highlight the rights of everyone to willingly make informed decisions on whether they want children, when and how many they want without any prejudice (10). Informed choices can only be made in a setting where quality information and quality FP services can both be accessed within which the government recognizes the use of modern FP as a human right, stimulating the demand for modern FP leading to an increased percentage of demand satisfied by modern methods. The FP 2030 goal, the SDG 3.7 and SDG 5.6 align with rights-based FP approach to achieve this. Having established rights-based approach as the means to satisfy the demands of women for modern FP, we need to understand the trend of the main indicators for modern FP across different regions of the world including SSA among Women of Reproductive Age (WRA) from the 1990s till date.

1.2 Modern Contraceptive Prevalence Rate (mCPR)

The proportion of all WRA using a modern FP method, called the modern Contraceptive Prevalence Rate (mCPR) increased globally from 36% in 1990 to 44% in 2019. During the same period, the proportion of women using traditional FP methods around the world fell from 6% to 4% (12). In 2012, 645 million women in SSA and SA used modern FP methods, an additional 42 million compared to 2008 (13). In 2016, an additional 30.2 million women were using modern FP methods compared to 2012 in LMICs: Africa, Asia and Latin America. In Africa, these figures were due to population growth rather than an increased proportion of modern FP users (mCPR) for example, in Nigeria, the WRA grew yearly by more than 1 million (14). However, the additional users in Latin America and Asia were as a result of an increase in mCPR. While mCPR is an important indicator of modern FP use in any population, , it has some limitations. Between 2012 and 2017, despite Africa witnessing a 44% total additional users, and the mCPR was disproportionately at 27%, it is still the region with the highest mCPR growth rate. There was a 12% increase in South and Eastern Africa followed by 0.8% increase in West Africa and 0.2-0.4% in South Asia although Asia has higher mCPR compared to Africa (15).

To better understand the context of growth rate in mCPR, experts developed an S-curve pattern for growth from analysis of trends of mCPR in LMICs (Figure 1). In this S-curve, there is low prevalence and slow growth positioned on one end, with high prevalence and low growth on the other, while there is a middle stage of possibly rapid growth (16). This S-curve is a very useful model for countries to assess their trends over the years using the three stages and identify areas for intervention at the required level of the health system; macro, meso or micro (15). Between 1990 and 2018 Nigeria has remained within Stage 1 alongside Somalia, while Ghana was in Stage 2 and Kenya in Stage 3. Within the 28-year period, the mCPR among WRA in Nigeria increased from 3.8% to 10.5% (14). To take Nigeria to Stage 2, there is need for increased political will towards FP using rights-based approach in encouraging demand for modern FP and optimizing the delivery of modern FP services nationwide based on the figure 1 below (15). This indicator mCPR is the use of modern FP among all women even those who are pregnant or those who want children. Moreover, there are more specific indicators, such as “need for modern FP”, “unmet need for modern FP” and “demand satisfied by modern method” including the “method mix”.

Nigeria's mCPR is marked in red

Note: The mCPR percentages listed in this figure are among currently married women.

Source: Track20 (2017)

Figure 1: The S-curve pattern of mCPR growth for married women

1.3 Need for Family Planning

The indicator “need for FP” measures proportion of all women of reproductive age who do not want to get pregnant or who want to delay pregnancy including women using modern FP. This indicator is vital in order to achieve the SDG 3.7 target of universal access to modern FP, however, there are not sufficient studies with evidence to capture the trends or point estimates globally or within countries. Among the 1.9 billion WRA worldwide in 2019, 1.1 billion had a need for FP (16,17). It was estimated that service delivery that would meet all women’s reproductive health care needs including modern FP would cost an annual amount of \$69 billion in LMICs. Looking at the current annual cost, this amount accounts for 83% annual increase. On a per capita consideration, it is \$4.80 increase per year (18). Hence there is

need for increased health financing to embark on FP programs with the aim of empowering women as well. Among those who need FP only few of these needs get satisfied by modern methods, hence the indicator “demand satisfied by modern methods exists” to measure effectively the use of modern FP in any given population.

1.4 Demand satisfied by modern methods

Within the SDGs, the target of SDG 3.7 is monitored by the indicator “demand satisfied by modern methods”. This is stated in the SDG indicator 3.7.1 as: “Proportion of women of reproductive age (aged 15-49 years) who have their need for family planning satisfied with modern methods” (2). According to the United Nations, setting a target of 100% for demand satisfied by modern methods is almost impossible, because women have several reasons for not using modern methods such as religious beliefs, trust for traditional FP methods, fear of unfavorable side effects. Therefore, the 75% benchmark was set by the SDG to be the goal for demand satisfied by modern methods in LMICs. Globally, the percentage of demand satisfied by modern methods among women of reproductive age was 78% (19). In 2020, while Eastern and South-Eastern Asia were at the level of 86.2% compared to their 2016 level of 77%, SSA was at the level of 39.5% in 2018 compared to their 2016 level of 23% in Central and 38% in West Africa (14,20). Using the most recent Demographic and Health Survey (DHS) in Nigeria from 2018, 34% of total demand was satisfied by modern methods. Demand satisfied and mCPR are both calculated among users of modern FP methods, but demand satisfied is different because it focuses on (has as the denominator) only women with a need for FP, while mCPR includes all women, with or without need for FP. The next indicator - unmet need for FP - which is equally specific to measure the extent of use of modern FP among women who are in need of FP.

1.5 Unmet Need for FP

Unmet need for FP measures fertile women and couples’ non-use of modern FP when they want to limit or delay childbirth including pregnant or postpartum women whose last pregnancy was either mistimed or unintended (21). Globally, from 1990 to 2010, unmet need for FP declined from 15.5% to 12.3% and in most parts of the world, Latin America and South Asia, unmet need for FP is around 10%. However, in Africa, it is 20% (22). In 2020, among the 923 million WRA who did not want to get pregnant in LMICs, 218 million of them had unmet need for modern FP. It is disproportionately high among adolescents (15–19 years) at 43%, in comparison to all women 15–49 (24%) (18). Among of the six countries with the world highest unmet need for FP, four are in SSA, they include: the Democratic Republic of the Congo, Uganda, Nigeria, and Kenya (19).

Unmet need for modern FP also includes women (or their partners) using traditional methods of contraception. Studies from Nigeria, Afghanistan, Papua New Guinea, Zambia, Bangladesh have shown that accessing FP services in Africa and Asia can be more difficult for women because of weak negotiating power within their households, gender-based violence, income, employment status, level of education as well as partner's level of education (23,24). Unmet need for FP in any country shows the level of the government's dedication to family planning (25). The modern methods the WRA are using is the next indicator to unpack.

1.6 Method mix

Cairo's declaration on population development from September 1994 highlighted the access of several cost-effective and efficacious FP methods to all women and their partners as a human right (9). Hence, it becomes imperative to this study to examine the contraceptive method mix, which is different across the regions worldwide. The uses of traditional methods has decreased significantly but the prevalence is still 11% of all users (26). Among modern methods, while most are reversible, few are irreversible and there exist varied failure rates. Therefore, the modern FP methods used in any given population called the method mix is a critical indicator to determine the effectiveness of a woman or her partner's desire to avoid unwanted pregnancy (27), as well as the accessibility of a range of contraceptive options. In most parts of Asia and Latin America, female sterilization is the most used modern FP method while it is one of the least used in Australia, Europe and Northern America, Africa and Western Asia. Contrary to most parts of the world, between 1995 and 2015, injectables and implants are increasingly used in SSA, Latin America and South East Asia, while oral contraceptives are on the decline (28). In a research using National surveys from 1960-2019, female sterilization was found most prevalent in Asia (39%) and in Latin America (31%), the pill in the Middle East/North Africa (32%), and the injectables in SSA (36%) while condom use increased in some high HIV-prevalent countries (26).

1.7 Context of Nigeria

In spite of Nigeria benefiting from several investments towards FP from INGOs, private sector and economic growth in Southern Nigeria, the effects are not spread country-wide (29). The Northern Nigeria has been lagging behind due to poor infrastructural development, poor leadership and long-term insecurity. The SDG 3.7 highlights the integration of SRH services into National strategies and programs, hence there is the need to understand the National policies around FP as well as the impact of INGOs in Nigeria towards FP.

1.7.1 National Population Policy I and II

The Arusha Conference held in Tanzania in 1984 produced a template for African countries to formulate policies addressing population crisis (30). This led to the Nigerian government in 1988, setting its first National Population Policy (NPP I) in motion: called “National Policy on Population for Development, Unity, Progress and Self Reliance” (1988-2000) unofficially called “the four-child policy”. This policy aimed at reducing parity by year 2000 to 4 children per women, restricting marriage age to 18 years old for women, advocating for 2 years birth-spacing and for pregnancies to be limited within 18-35 years. For the implementation of this policy, US\$100 million was set as the cost for FP service delivery and FP counseling. USAID funded this project with \$67 million. Efforts were made to utilize the local contexts in implementing this policy nevertheless it failed (31). The policy was revised in 2004 to becoming the “National policy on Population for sustainable development” (NPP II). The policy imbibed the access to contraception as human right issue thus encompassing equity, health and development of the people in its formulation. The objectives of this revised policy (2004-2015) relate to FP, health and education. The FP targets include: reducing national population growth rate to 2% or lower by 2015; reducing total fertility rate by at least 0.6 children every five years; and increasing mCPR by at least 2% per year (32). Even though, this policy encompassed right-based FP approach, it again failed to accomplish its targets (31).

1.7.2 FP Blueprint and Nigeria’s FP 2030

Following the 2012 London Summit on FP, while the time for the revised NPP has not elapsed, FGoN in 2013, launched a more specific target for FP and called it FP Blueprint. This had an initial ambitious goal to raise the nation’s mCPR to 36% by 2018 but it failed, giving rise to a new blueprint (2020-2024) to raise the mCPR to a more achievable goal of 27% by 2024. However, at the end of 2021, mCPR in Nigeria was at 11.7% (33) which led to FP2030. The FGoN, through National Population Commission streamlined the NPP with the creation of “FP2030” which is aimed at sustainability of access to FP services nationwide mirroring the goals of the global FP2030. Nigeria’s FP2030 goal aligned with SDG 3.7 in the aspect of equity which is “By the end of 2030, Nigeria envisions a country where everyone including adolescents, young people, populations affected by crisis and other vulnerable populations are able to make informed choices, have equitable and affordable access to quality family planning and participate as equals in society’s development” (34). The mCPR target of FP2030 aligned with the FP Blueprint’s target of 27% but the timeline corresponded with the SDG’s of 2030. Financing this target would be locally sourced with allocation of at least 1% of the yearly budgets of FG and State governments. However, the recent army banditry in Nigeria has affected financing health care as insecurity issues plagues economic development in Northern Nigeria (35).

1.7.3 Financial Commitments and Role of INGOs

The financial commitments of FGoN towards implementing policies has not been adequate. In 2011, the Nigerian government made a commitment to provide FP services at no cost at government-owned health facilities with the “Free Family Planning Commodity Policy”, however, implementation have been poor (36). Following this policy, the FGoN embarked on large-scale procurement and distribution of contraceptives to all the 36 states and the FCT Abuja. To manage this complex national distribution of free contraceptives, the FMoH initiated the FP Blueprint in 2012. This initiative was committed to increase finances towards FP products and acquire cost-effective and reliable contraceptives as well as manage the chain of supply of contraceptives. INGOs such as UNFPA, GHSC-PSM, provided some technical help with this (37). Nigeria would need \$603 million between 2013 and 2018 to achieve CPR of 36% (36). In 2016, only 13.3% of estimated budget for FP products, was allocated by the FGoN. The rest of the budget of \$12.9 million was covered by donors namely DFID, UNFPA and USAID. In 2018, donors again funded Nigeria’s FP budget with \$13.9 million (38). Yearly, there is a progressive decline in finance allocation for health budget, and the right use of the the finance for the appropriate purposes. Till date Nigeria is still very donor-dependent which cannot be sustained to cater for the FP needs of about 40 million WRA and their partners (39).

Research has shown that FP programs irrespective of socio-demographic and socio-economic inequalities enhances increase in demand satisfied by modern methods which was part of the SDG 3.7 as a means of achieving universal access (40). In Nigeria, PPFN was created in 1959 as an extension of IPPF founded in 1952. IPPF is a global advocate for the SRH rights for all and is present in over 146 countries (41). Despite all these interventions and programs, Nigeria is still lagging behind in achieving its National targets much less the SDG targets. In contrast to this, other countries in SSA such as Zimbabwe, Malawi and Kenya scaled up their mCPR significantly to high prevalence in 2020 with FP programs (40).

From 1990 till date, there has been a large body of evidence about mCPR and unmet need in Nigeria but little is known about the the demand satisfied by modern methods and even much less is known about the need for FP. We know that the levels of unmet need for FP in Nigeria is high, there are gaps within implementation of policies in Nigeria, there exists social determinants that influence the use of modern method for example Northern versus Southern Nigeria, the inequalities between men and women that affects majority of the Nigerian WRA in accessing contraceptives. However, the time trends of the indicators of FP is not yet known. Understanding how mCPR, unmet need and method mix change over women’s life course is the gap of knowledge my thesis seek to fill. Comparing Kenya’s mCPR of 53% to Nigeria’s mCPR below 15% shows that Kenya’s economic growth and effective

national FP strategies has contributed greatly to their mCPR. In Nigeria, however, many attempts to implement FP targeted health policies have met several bottlenecks which gives a window of opportunity to employ an evidenced-based trend analysis to inform subsequent policy formulation and implementation (14).

1.8 Justification

I am a Nigerian and a Ukraine-trained Medical Doctor with work experience in Belgium, hence my professional years have been outside Nigeria. Due to this, I chose to write my thesis about Nigeria using a methodological approach & historical analysis. I chose to analyze trend of the indicators of FP because of my work experience in Belgium. At the Institute of Tropical Medicine, Antwerp in the Department of Public Health, Maternal and Reproductive Health Unit, I participated in two research projects. The first was a review of postpartum care guidelines globally (qualitative document review), while the second study was about the provision of maternal care in large African cities, including in Nigeria.

CHAPTER TWO: OBJECTIVE

2.1 General objective

The objective of this study is to analyze changes over time in the use of modern FP in Nigeria. I will take a synthetic cohort approach and use five Nigeria population-representative surveys from 1990-2018 to estimate several indicators of FP use for women born between 1971 and 1975. For each of the five surveys, I will analyze these indicators for women born between 1971-75 and thus chart a synthetic birth cohort of women as they age over their reproductive lifespan (from 15-19 at the time of 1990 survey, to 43-47 years at the time of the 2018 survey), and examine how these indicators change over time.

The five key indicators of interest are:

- 1) The use of modern FP methods among all women (mCPR).
- 2) The extent of "need for modern FP" (that is women who do not want to be pregnant in the next 2 years) among all women.
- 3) The extent of demand for FP satisfied among women who are in need of modern FP.
- 4) The extent of unmet need for FP, among women who are in need of modern FP.
- 5) The method mix among users of modern FP methods.

I will use these findings to identify gaps and recommend strengthening of SRH policies in Nigeria to address those gaps.

2.1.1 Specific objectives

- To describe the trend of the use of modern FP methods over time and among those in need of modern FP, to see how their demand is satisfied as women born between 1971-75 age from 15 through 47 years in Nigeria.
- To examine the mix of different modern methods of FP used over time as women grow through their reproductive years from 15 to 47 years old in Nigeria.

2.2 Hypothesis

- As women get older, the use of modern FP methods increases among all women.
- As women get older, the percentage of women in need for FP rises and then declines toward later age group.
- As women get older, the percentage of women in need who have demand satisfied by modern FP methods increases while the percentage of women who have unmet need reduces.
- Additionally, regarding method mix, the older women get, the higher their preference for a long-acting reversible FP method such as IUD over short acting method such as condom. This is because I hypothesize that a larger share of older women want to limit childbearing compared to younger women who might be predominantly using FP to space pregnancies.

CHAPTER THREE: METHODS

3.1 Data sampling and Data Collection

I analyzed data from all (five) available Nigeria DHS, namely: 1990, 2003, 2008, 2013, and 2018. The DHS are cross-sectional nationally representative household surveys usually covering 5,000 to 30,000 households. Nigeria's DHS covered 10,000 households in 1990 to 42,000 in 2018. The sampling design used by the DHS is stratified probability sampling. Stratification was achieved by separating each of the 36 states and the FCT Abuja into urban and rural areas leading to 74 strata and this was consistent for all the years. In all five surveys except one (2013 DHS), the samples were selected independently in every stratum through a two-stage cluster design. In the first stage of sampling, a probability proportional to size was used to select the cluster while in the second sampling stage, a fixed number of households were selected in every cluster by an equal probability systematic sampling. However, in the 2013 DHS, there was a three-stage selection as opposed to a two-stage selection in the other surveys. In the 2013 DHS, there was an initial stage of locality selection within each urban and rural stratum followed by the two stages in the other surveys namely the cluster selection by probability proportional to size and then the selection of fixed number of households in every cluster. The number of clusters were 299 in 1990 DHS, 365 in 2003 DHS, 888 in 2008 DHS, 904 in 2013 DHS and 1440 in 2018 DHS with an average of 40 households per cluster. This sampling design of multi-level cluster strategy must be accounted for in statistical analyses.

In the DHS, standard model questionnaires are used, which countries can adapt by adding optional modules, questions or response options. Manuals and technical assistance ensure that the survey procedures followed in each country are similar, allowing data to be compared across countries. Surveys are normally conducted over 18-20 months, with several months of data collection which are adapted to each country's circumstances. The surveys include questions on household and individual characteristics, fertility and FP, maternal and child health, certain infections like malaria and HIV contributing to maternal and infant mortality. Respondents eligible for individual interviews are either ever-married women (and their spouses) or all WRA (15-49 years) and men (15-54 years) who are usual members of the selected households or spent the night before the survey in the selected households.

3.2 Study design /Population

From each survey round, I included all women born between 1971-75. This creates a “synthetic” cohort of women, meaning that I examined a 5-year birth cohort of women, but not by following the same women across their reproductive lifespan, but by having repeat cross-sectional, representative data on this birth cohort from each survey round. I chose the birth cohort of 1971-1975 because the women were 15-19 years old at the earliest available survey; enabling me to follow this synthetic cohort from the beginning (age 15-19) to nearly end of their reproductive age (which is usually marked by the age 49 years) at the most recent survey of 2018. The ages of the women at the five surveys were 15-19 years (1990 DHS), 28-32 years (2003 DHS), 33-37 years (2008 DHS), 38-42 years (2013 DHS), 43-47 years (2018 DHS). The women at ages 20-27 years and women at ages 48-49 years were excluded from my sample because there was no available Nigeria DHS that represented their age group. Note that a cohort study design would have required me to follow up the women born between 1971-75 throughout their reproductive years which is not possible within the timeline of my thesis, hence the study design of synthetic cohort rather than the typical cohort.

3.3 Definitions

Two of the key indicators in this study will be described because they cannot be directly derived from the variables in the DHS. Afterwards, the definitions of all the key indicators with how they were calculated from variables in the DHS will be shown in the following paragraphs.

3.3.1 Women in "need for FP"

In FP research, especially estimates derived from DHS, “women who are in need of FP” is a sub-set of all women of reproductive age (15-49 years), defined as those who are sexually active (non currently married/ non cohabiting women who reported having had recent sexual intercourse and all married women) who are fecund, not postpartum amenorrheic, and who do not want to get pregnant within the next 2 years. Among women in need of FP are two categories of women: those with “met need for modern FP” and those with “unmet need for FP”. The percentage of women with met need among women with need for FP is known as “demand satisfied”. The percentage of women with unmet need for FP among women in need for FP is known as “unmet need”. The percentage of demand satisfied and unmet need added together is 100%. Hence the number of women in need of FP is the denominator for both unmet need for FP and demand satisfied by modern method.

Adapted from Bradley’s definition of unmet need (21). The questions women were asked to determine unmet need includes:

- Are you or your partner currently doing something or using any method to delay or avoid getting pregnant? IF YES: Exclude (no unmet need).
- Did you want your current pregnancy (if respondent is pregnant) or do you want to get pregnant the last time you got pregnant within the last 2 years? IF YES: Exclude (no unmet need).
- Did you want your current pregnancy (if respondent is pregnant) or do you want your last birth within the last 2 years at all? IF NO: Include (unmet need for limiting).
- Did you want your current pregnancy (if respondent is pregnant) or do you want your last birth within the last 2 years later? IF NO: Include (unmet need for spacing).

The following questions were asked from women who are NOT pregnant or postpartum amenorrheic.

- Since you have been married (if respondents are married), have you had any children in the past 5 years? If NO, ask the next question below:
- Did you ever use any contraception in the past 5 years? If NO: Exclude as “infecund” (no unmet need).
- Do you want children in the future? If “CANNOT GET PREGNANT”: Exclude as “infecund” (no unmet need).
- Why are you not using contraception: If “MENOPAUSAL/HYSTERECTOMY”: Exclude as “infecund” (no unmet need).
- When was your last period: If ≥ 6 months: Exclude as “infecund” (no unmet need).
- When was your last period: If “MENOPAUSAL/HYSTERECTOMY or “NEVER MENSTRUATED”: Exclude as “infecund” (no unmet need).
- When was your last period: If “BEFORE MY LAST BIRTH (when last birth is more than five years ago”): Exclude as “infecund” (no unmet need).

Unmet Need for FP was also defined according to Bradley et al 2012 (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Unmet need for FP among currently married women defined by Bradley et al

DHS revised the definition of unmet need in 2012. Using the revised definition of unmet need for FP (21):

- Unmet need is calculated the same way in DHS surveys following 2012 so in our analysis we statistically computed this new calculation in the unmet need variable in the 1990, 2003 and 2008 surveys.
- Unmet need can be used to reliably track trends over time and compare estimates across countries.

3.3.2 Modern FP method

This includes medications or surgical procedures which interfere with the progression of sexual activity to pregnancy. Modern contraceptive methods include barrier methods such as male and female condoms, diaphragm; hormonal contraceptives that include oral pills, injectables, implants, foam and jelly; natural hormonal contraceptive which is lactational amenorrhea and intrauterine device (IUD) (42).

Questions women were asked to know the method used includes:

1. What method did you or your partner use? Respondent chooses from the letters “A to Y” which represents all methods, modern and traditional.
2. PROBE: Did you or your partner use any other method to prevent pregnancy? If YES, respondents choose from the list “A to Y” and for these women, only one (the most effective method) would be captured. For example, if a woman is using pills and her partner is using condoms, she will be registered as a pill user (the condom, considered as a less effective method compared to pills would be disregarded and not recorded).

Based on the DHS 2018, **modern methods** captured in v312 includes: male and female condoms, oral pills, injectables, implants, intrauterine devices (IUDs), male and female sterilization. The other methods including diaphragm, use of foam and jelly, lactational amenorrhea method (LAM), emergency contraception and other modern method were classified as “*other modern methods*” in this analysis. **Traditional methods** include withdrawal, standard days method, rhythm method and other traditional methods.

DHS further classified modern methods into short-acting methods (**SAM**) and long-acting reversible contraceptives (**LARC**) and permanent methods. SAM are methods with less than six months of contraceptive efficiency such as male and female condom, diaphragm, oral pills, foam or jelly, lactational amenorrhea and emergency contraception). LARC are methods with more than six months of contraceptive efficiency such as implants, injectables, IUDs. **Permanent methods** are methods that last for the lifetime such as female and male sterilization.

Table 1 includes the definitions of the five key indicators of interest linked to the objectives of this thesis. The questions that were asked to generate these variables were all asked as at the time of the survey.

Table 1: Definition of five key indicators analyzed in this report

Indicators	Definition and calculation	DHS variables used	Source
Modern Contraceptive Prevalence Rate (mCPR)	<p>Percentage of all women who are currently using, or whose sexual partner is currently using, at least one modern method of contraception, regardless of the method being used.</p> <p>This can be further divided into: Using for spacing and Using for limiting.</p> <p><i>Numerator: total number of users of modern contraceptive methods</i></p> <p><i>Denominator: WRA</i></p> <p>(Regardless of whether women are exposed to sex or not.) Expressed as a percentage.</p>	<p>V312 (this captured the type of method used at time of survey).</p> <p>The numerator was calculated by summing up all the users of modern FP users in v312 in each of the age specific sample.</p>	<p>United Nations (43)</p>
Need for FP	<p>Percentage of all women who are sexually active but do not want to get pregnant in the next two years.</p> <p>Need for spacing: This is the percentage of women who do not want to get pregnant within the next 2 years of their last birth and want to use FP. (DHS 2018)</p> <p>Need for limiting: This is the percentage of women who do not want to get pregnant at all after their last birth and want to use FP. (DHS 2018)</p> <p><i>Numerator: Women in need for FP</i></p> <p><i>Denominator: WRA</i></p> <p>Expressed as a percentage.</p>	<p>V626a</p> <p>The numerator was calculated as the sum of unmet need (for spacing and limiting) with the users for spacing and limiting. All these were provided in v626a.</p> <p>It is important to note that this indicator is not captured by any singular variable in the DHS.</p>	<p>United Nations (43)</p>
Demand for FP satisfied by modern methods	<p>The percentage of WRA who have their need for FP satisfied with modern methods among those in need of FP to stop or delay childbearing.</p> <p><i>Numerator: Current contraceptive use (all modern method users)</i></p> <p><i>Denominator: Women in need of FP.</i></p>	<p>V626a; v312</p> <p>V626a provided the denominator for this indicator while the modern methods users in v312 was the numerator. Note that this was the numerator for mCPR as well. Also</p>	<p>WHO (44)</p>

	Expressed as a percentage		the numerator for need for FP is the denominator for demand satisfied.
Unmet need for FP	<p>The percentage of women of reproductive age, either married or in a union who want to stop or delay childbearing but are not using a modern method of contraception.</p> <p><i>Numerator: Women with unmet need for either spacing and limiting</i></p> <p><i>Denominator: Women in need of FP.</i></p> <p>Expressed as a percentage</p>	<p>V626a; v312</p> <p>V626a provided the denominator just like for demand satisfied. The numerator was also estimated from v626a by summing up unmet need (for spacing and limiting) and unmet need for modern methods who are the users of traditional methods in v312.</p>	<p>United Nations (43)</p>
Method mix	<p>The distribution of all current modern contraceptive users by method.</p> <p>For each method, this indicator is calculated as:</p> <p><i>Numerator: Number of users of a specific method.</i></p> <p><i>Denominator: Total number of modern contraceptive users.</i></p> <p>Expressed as a percentage</p>	<p>v312</p> <p>The numerator was provided by v312 as well as the denominator.</p>	<p>USAID (45)</p>

3.3.3 Definition of other variables used in analysis.

The changing socio-demographic characteristics of the 1971-75 cohort over the five surveys were assessed by level of education, marital status, parity, currently working at the time of the survey, residence and religion. These characteristics were important in the access to modern FP in Nigeria (46). **The level of education** of the women in our birth cohort is essential because generally education improves capabilities and is strongly associated with various socioeconomic variables such as lifestyle, income, and fertility. The levels were assessed using the v106 variable in the DHS data sets and they included: *no education, primary education, or secondary education and higher education*. **Marital status** of the women at the time of survey was also assessed and for simplicity, we regrouped the several categories (as provided by v501 in the DHS data sets) as '*married or cohabiting*' or '*not married or cohabiting*'. The second category of not married or cohabiting included women who were never married, and women who were previously married or cohabiting but were divorced, widowed, or separated from their partners at the time of survey.

The total number of children a woman has given birth to is called **parity**. **Parity is an important demographic measure resulting from fertility thereby closely associated with modern FP use and intention to use**. The v201 variable from the DHS data sets provided us the values at the time of each survey, and I regrouped this continuous variable into four categories: *0 child, 1 or 2 children, 3 or 4 children, and 5 or more children*. The mean and median number of children of each age group in the birth cohort was estimated. **The residence** of the women to see their living conditions was also assessed as provided by v025 from the DHS data sets to be either *rural or urban*. **The current work status** provided by variable v714 of the DHS data sets as at the time of the survey was examined and the outcome was 'Yes' if the women were currently working or 'No' if they were not. Finally, **the religion** of the women was described as these influence their perception about using modern FP.

3.4 Analysis

The statistical analyses were done using Software R version 4.1.3. In the DHS data used, the sampling design was a multi-level cluster survey, which often over-samples certain areas due to the non-proportional allocation of the sample to the different states in Nigeria. The sample is unbalanced (disproportional) by urban-rural residence, different states in Nigeria, as well as the possible differences in response rates across the states. This was adjusted for by using the sampling weights provided by the DHS for each survey, to generate correct representative estimates at both the national and domain levels.

I used descriptive analysis. Initially, I assessed at the socio-demographic characteristics of the women in the 1971-75 birth cohort as they age from 15-19 to 43-47 using the 5 Nigeria DHS datasets by level of education, marital status, parity, employment at the time of the survey, residence and religion. Analysis of each socio-demographic category was done using percentages and 95% confidence intervals (CI). Additionally, further analysis of parity was conducted by estimating the mean and median number of children. Following this, changes over time of the increasing age-groups in the 1971-75 birth cohort using the five key indicators from Table 1 (**mCPR, need for FP, demand satisfied by modern methods, unmet need for FP, method mix**) were analyzed with percentages and 95% CIs. Finally, the intention of using FP whether for spacing or for limiting was analyzed, as well as the intention of using by method mix using percentages and 95% CIs. The findings of these descriptive analyses were shown in tables and figures.

In each data set, I excluded the missing values from the sample size before analyzing with percentages and 95% CIs. Looking into each survey, it is important to note that, as the year progressed, the amount of missing data reduced gradually except in the survey representing the 15-19, 33-37 and 38-42 age group. In our socio-demographic analysis, there was no missingness except in the currently working variable (v714) and religion variable (v130). In the currently working variable, among the 33-37 age-group there were missing 20 respondents and among the 38-42 age-group they were 35 respondents. In the religion variable, there was missing 1 respondent among the women at 15-19 years, 24 respondents among the women at 33-37 and 35 respondents among the women at 38-42. In the analysis of the key indicators, among the women in my study, there was a very little missingness in the total number of respondents to the questions related to the key indicators and consequently there were 1552 out 1553 women using modern and traditional methods of FP. I excluded this small missingness in my sample before analyzing.

3.5 Ethical approval

Using this secondary data (DHS) does not require ethical approval by the Ethics Committee of ITM as the survey received the Nigerian government's approval. Also, the DHS obtain informed consent and assure respondents of confidentiality.

CHAPTER FOUR: RESULTS

4.1 Description of the sample

The sample size of women in the 1971-1975 birth cohort, as they aged from when women were at 15-19 years in 1990 DHS to when women were at 43-47 years in 2018 DHS, ranged from 1,127 on the 2003 survey to 4,156 on the 2013 survey. I looked at the socio-demographic characteristics across these age groups and the result of this analysis with percentages and 95% confidence intervals are shown in Table 2 below.

Table 2: Characteristics of the women born in 1971-75, by survey

Survey year Age of women Sample size	1990 15-19 1,553		2003 28-32 1,127		2008 33-37 3,794		2013 38-42 4,156		2018 43-47 3,455	
	%	95% CI	%	95% CI						
Education										
None	35.0	29.1-40.8	40.4	35.8-45.1	35.7	33.5-37.9	43.9	41.2-46.6	43.0	40.7-45.3
Primary	32.5	28.8-36.5	22.7	19.5-26.2	26.0	24.2-27.8	24.3	22.5-26.3	24.3	22.6-26.2
Secondary	32.1	27.8-36.7	28.8	24.3-33.8	26.4	24.6-28.3	22.9	21.0-24.7	22.7	21.0-24.6
Higher	0.5	0.1-1.1	8.1	5.5-11.9	12.0	10.5-13.6	9.0	7.6-10.5	10.0	8.7-11.4
Currently married/ cohabiting										
Yes	37.5	33.4-41.7	89.2	86.4-91.4	90.9	89.7-91.9	89.9	88.5-91.1	84.5	83.0-85.9
No	62.5	58.3-66.6	10.9	8.6-13.6	9.1	8.1-10.3	10.1	8.9-11.5	15.5	14.1-17.0
Parity										
0	77.3	74.2-80.1	11.8	9.7-14.4	5.8	4.9-6.8	4.6	3.8-5.6	3.2	2.6-3.9
1-2	21.7	19.0-24.6	21.4	18.3-25.0	13.7	12.4-15.2	8.7	7.7-9.8	9.8	8.6-11.2
3-4	1.03	0.6-1.9	31.2	28.0-34.6	26.6	24.9-28.2	20.8	19.2-22.5	19.0	17.4-20.6
5+			35.5	31.7-39.6	53.9	51.8-56.1	65.9	63.8-68.0	68.1	66.1-69.9
Median	0		4		5		6		6	
Mean	0.3		3.5		5.0		5.7		6.2	
Residence										
Urban	28.2	24.4-32.3	33.5	29.1-38.2	37.4	35.3-39.5	42.3	39.8-44.8	46.6	44.2-48.9
Rural	71.8	67.8-75.6	66.5	61.8-70.9	62.6	60.5-64.7	57.8	55.2-60.2	53.4	51.1-55.8
Currently working					n=3774		n=4121			
Yes	25.2	21.1-29.8	68.2	64.4-71.9	76.5	74.7-78.3	82.3	80.6-83.8	83.5	81.9-85.0
No	74.8	70.3-78.9	31.6	28.0-35.4	23.0	21.3-24.7	17.7	16.2-19.4	16.5	15.0-18.1
Religion	n=1552				n=3770		n=4121			
Christianity	53.3	47.6-58.9	48.2	43.0-53.4	54.1	51.7-56.5	47.4	44.6- 50.2	50.0	47.4-52.7
Islam	43.6	38.1-49.3	50.5	45.4-55.6	43.8	41.4-46.2	51.4	48.5-54.2	49.3	46.7-52.0
Others	3.0	1.6-5.6	1.3	0.6-2.7	1.5	1.1-2.0	1.2	0.8-1.9	0.7	0.4-1.0

4.1.1 Level of education and marital status

More than a third of the women in the 1971-75 birth cohort had no formal education (in any survey year). The percentage who acquired only primary education varied from 32.5% when women were at their 15-19 years to 24.3% when they were at their 43-47 years. Similarly, the percentage who acquired only secondary education varied from 32.1% when women were at their 15-19 years to 22.7% when they were at their 43-47 years. The percentage of women with higher level of education was the same as the women grew older except when women were at their 15-19 years as they could not have attained higher education at that age.

As women in the 1971-75 birth cohort aged from when women were at their 15-19 to when women were at their 28-32, the percentage who reported being married or cohabiting increased sharply from 37% to 89%. Only once women reached the age group of 43-48, did the percentage married/cohabiting decline slightly to 84%. More of the women, about two-thirds were not married or not cohabiting at their youngest age group of 15-19 but when women were at their 33-37 years, 91% of them (the highest) were married or cohabiting. Among the women who were married or cohabiting, a very large proportion of the women were married compared to those cohabiting (not shown) while among the women not married or not cohabiting, a large proportion were never married except among the 38-

42 and 43-47 age group where majority were widowed, and a few others were separated or divorced (not shown).

4.1.2 Parity and Residence

As women got older (from 15-19 to 43-47), the number of children they ever gave birth to increased from a median number of zero (0) to a median of six (6) children, and a mean number from 0.3 to 6.2. Even though most of the women in their youngest age group had no child, a little above a fifth had 1 or 2 children, while a small percentage (1.0%) had 3 or 4 children. As the women aged, at their 43-47 years, an 58% had 5 or more children.

The residence of the women stayed highest at rural areas throughout their reproductive years. The highest percentage of rural dwellers 71%, were women at their 15-19 years. This percentage declined gradually hitting the lowest of 53.4% when women were at their 43-47 years which is still relatively higher than urban dwellers. The change from rural to urban was rapid, a huge change in just one generation which shows the rapid urbanization that has occurred through the 28 years of the women in my study.

4.1.3 Currently working and religion

More of the women in my analysis were currently working asides from when women were at their youngest age group, they had the least percentage of 25.2%. As women aged, the percentage of currently working increased progressively from 68.2% when women were at their 28-32 years to 84% when they were at their 43-47 years.

The religion of the women was mostly Christianity and Islam, with a very few others such as traditional worshipers or women with no religion at all. As women aged, the percentage between Christianity and Islam were almost similar in any year. Religion is not expected to change much as women age because once the women belong to a religion, they remain in it except very few who might convert to a different religion, but this would be very insignificant.

4.2 Results of key indicators

4.2.1 Use of modern family planning (mCPR)

When the 1971-75 birth cohort were at their 15-19 years, a very small percentage (1.9%) reported using a modern method of FP. This sharply spiked with an almost five-fold increase to 9.4% when women were at their 28-32 years and continue to rise gradually when women were at their 38-42 years, falling steadily when women were at their 43-47 years. Figure 3 below shows that the curve of the use of modern FP is almost bell-shaped, with women of age-groups 33-37 and 38-42 forming the highest point. There are overlaps of the 95% CIs for women at the 33-37 and 38-42 age groups as well as for women at 28-32 and 43-47 age groups.

Figure 3: Percentage and confidence intervals of all women in birth cohort 1971-75 using modern FP, by age.

4.2.2 Need for family planning

The need for modern FP is the common denominator in calculating unmet need for FP and demand satisfied by modern method. Within our 1971-75 birth cohort, the need for FP among all women was the lowest (14.6%) when women were at their 15-19 years. This percentage increased sharply to 33.2% when women were at their 28-32 years and then slowly increased when they were at their 33-37 years

at which age group the need for FP was the highest at 41.5%. This percentage dropped gradually when women were at their 38-42 years, falling gradually again as the women were at their 43-47 years almost to the same level as the 28-32 age group. There are overlaps of the 95% CIs for women as they aged from being 28-32 years to when women were at their 43-47 years. This is shown graphically in figure 4 below.

Figure 4: Percentage of all women who were in need for FP, by age

4.2.3 Demand satisfied by modern methods and unmet need for FP

The demand satisfied by modern methods and unmet need for modern methods in a given population adds up to 100%. Both indicators have a common denominator of women in need of modern FP methods. In the figure 5 below, as women in the 1971-75 birth cohort age from when they were at their 15-19 years to when they were at their 38-42 years, there was a gradual increase in the percentage of women who were in need of FP and who had their demand satisfied by modern methods met. However, this declined when women were at their 43-47 years. Vice versa, the unmet need for modern methods experienced a gradual decrease when women were at their 15-19 years to when they were at their 38-42 years and this increased when women were at their 43-47 years.

Figure 5: The percentage of women with unmet need and demand satisfied by modern methods (among women in need of modern FP), by age

4.2.4 Method mix among modern method users

Table 3 shows that as the women in the 1971-75 birth cohort got older, the most commonly used methods ranged from oral pills to condoms and then to injectables. Initially, when women were 15-19 years, about half of the FP users relied on oral contraceptives, followed by the male condoms, and other methods which comprised largely of foaming tablets (not shown). When women were 28-32 years, 39.6% of them relied on condoms, followed by oral pills and then other methods which was mostly lactational amenorrhea (not shown). When they were 33-37 years, 29.3% of women used condoms while 28.8% used injectables, followed by oral pills. Injectables became the most used FP method when women were 38-42 years (38.3%), followed by condoms and oral pills (17.5% and 16.3%, respectively). When the women in the birth cohort were 43-47 years, the most commonly used FP method was injectables (27.6%), followed by implants and IUDs (21.2 % and 17.2%, respectively).

Table 3: Method mix among the modern FP users

Survey year	1990		2003		2008		2013		2018	
Age range	15-19		28-32		33-37		38-42		43-47	
Women	37		109		479		583		337	
	%	95% CI								
Condom*	24.3	7.2- 57.0	39.6	33.8-45.7	29.3	24.4-34.7	17.5	14.1-21.5	9.51	6.5-13.7
Oral pills	49.3	25.8-73.1	21.3	17.7-25.2	17.3	13.7-21.6	16.3	12.8-20.5	10.5	7.3-15.0
Injectables	6.4	6.3-6.5	14.6	12.5-17.1	28.8	24.3-33.7	38.3	32.9-43.9	27.6	21.8-34.3
Implant	-		-		0.5	0.1-1.6	3.0	1.8-5.0	21.2	16.6-26.7
Intrauterine device	3.2	3.2-3.3	4.9	4.6-5.3	8.6	6.3-11.7	13.0	9.4-17.7	17.2	13.0-22.4
Sterilization*	0.0		0.7	0.6-0.7	2.9	1.8- 4.8	5.5	3.8-7.9	8.4	5.7-12.2
Other methods	16.7	16.4-17.0	18.9	15.1-23.5	12.6	9.5-16.5	6.4	4.5-9.1	5.5	3.0-9.9

*Male and female methods combined

4.2.5 Intention of spacing or limiting

The intention of using modern FP either for spacing or limiting was also analyzed. The use of FP for these purposes in a given population adds up to 100%, hence they are comparable. Youngest women with the age group 15-19 all used modern contraceptive methods for spacing (Figure 6). As women were 28-32 years, a little above three-fourths of them used modern FP for spacing while the remaining fourth used them for limiting. When women were 33-37 years, there was almost an equal distribution of them using modern FP for spacing and limiting. When women were 38-42 years, fewer of them, 21.8% used modern FP for spacing while 78.2% used modern FP for limiting. When women were older, 43-47 years, only a tenth of them used modern FP for spacing and the majority for limiting.

Figure 6: A stacked bar chart showing the percentage of women using modern FP methods for spacing and limiting by age.

4.2.6 Method mix for spacing

The method mix among the users of modern FP was also examined in terms of the intention of whether women wanted to space or limit childbearing. At the age of 15-19, women in the birth cohort all reported using FP for spacing. Among these women, Table 4 shows that oral pills were used by the majority (49.3%) of them, followed by condom (24.4%). When women were 28-32 years, the reverse was the case, 48.6% used condom followed by 23.8% using oral pills. When women got older, 33-38, 38-42 and 43-47 years, they used condom and injectables more for spacing than any other FP method. While 33-38 years old, they used condom more than injectables (36.9% and 25.3% respectively), whereas, while at 38-42 and 43-47 years, they used injectables more than condom, (40.8% and 25.1% respectively at 38-42 years and 33.7% and 24.3% respectively at 43-47 years).

Table 4: Modern contraceptive method mix among women using modern FP for spacing

Survey year	1990		2003		2008		2013		2018	
Age range	15-19		28-32		33-37		38-42		43-47	
Women	37		87		254		165		37	
	%	95% CI								
Condom*	24.4	7.2- 57.0	48.6	45.3-51.9	36.9	30.3-44.1	25.1	18.4-33.3	33.7	15.9-57.7
Oral pills	49.3	25.8-73.1	23.8	19.7-28.5	16.5	11.8-22.5	15.9	11.4-21.8	8.7	4.9-15.1
Injectables	6.4	6.3-6.5	7.9	5.5-11.4	25.3	20.1-31.3	40.8	34.0-48.2	24.3	17.3-33.1
Implant	0.0		0.0		0.0		1.5	0.5-4.9	7.5	3.0-17.6
Intrauterine devices	3.2	3.2-3.3	3.2	3.1-3.4	9.5	6.2-14.2	8.6	4.9-14.5	13.0	4.3-33.0
Sterilization*	0.0		0.0		0.0		0.0		0.0	
Other methods	16.7	16.4-17.0	16.4	13.6-19.7	11.9	8.2-17.0	8.0	4.7-13.4	12.8	5.2-28.1

*Male and female methods combined

4.2.7 Method mix for limiting

Among women using modern FP to limit, Table 5 shows that when women were 28-32 years, (since none of the women at 15-19 years used FP for limiting), injectables (36.4%) was the mostly used method followed by pills (10.3%). Injectables, continued to be the method used by most of the women when they were 33-37 years and older. For women 33-37 years old, injectables stood at 32.7% followed by the use of condom which was 20.9%. When women were 38-42 years, injectables stood at 37.3% followed by the use of oral pills which was used by 16.5% of them. Lastly, when women were 43-47 years, injectables users stood at 28.0% followed by implant users which was 22.7%.

Table 5 : Modern contraceptive method mix among women using modern FP for limiting

Survey year Age range Women	1990		2003		2008		2013		2018	
	15-19		28-32		33-37		38-42		43-47	
	-		22		225		418		300	
	%	95% CI	%	95% CI	%	95% CI	%	95% CI	%	95% CI
Condom*	-		10.3	7.5-13.9	20.9	15.3-28.0	14.5	11.0-18.9	6.9	4.4-10.6
Oral pills	-		12.9	1.3-62.3	18.2	13.3-24.3	16.5	12.3-21.6	10.7	7.2-15.6
Injectables	-		36.4	26.0-48.3	32.7	26.5-39.6	37.3	31.2-43.8	28.0	21.7-35.3
Implant	-		0.0		1.0	0.3- 3.4	3.6	2.0-6.3	22.7	17.7-28.7
Intrauterine devices	-		10.5	7.7-14.2	7.6	4.8-12.0	14.8	10.1-21.1	17.7	13.1-23.3
Sterilization*	-		2.8	2.1-3.8	6.1	3.8-9.8	7.6	5.2-11.1	9.3	6.5-13.1
Other methods	-		27.2	19.6-36.4	13.4	9.1-19.3	5.8	3.6-9.2	4.8	2.3-9.6

*Male and female methods combined

CHAPTER FIVE: DISCUSSION

This study examined the need for and use of modern FP methods for the cohort of 1971-75 over their reproductive life-course. This was done using five key indicators which captured the use of modern FP, the need for FP, the met need (demand satisfied), unmet need and mix of the FP methods used. The result of my analysis showing mCPR highest percentage as 13.8% shows Nigeria, has a very low mCPR and according to the Track 20 S-curve mCPR growth pattern and for the 28-year period, this can be categorized as a slow growth (15). Nigeria, being a partner country in FP2030 thus has a very huge responsibility to move its mCPR to Stage 2 which is mCPR of 15%-54% and then move to Stage 3 which is the expected stage for the partner countries of FP2030 by 2030 (15). My results also showing the highest percentage of the need for FP as 41.5% corresponds with the long-standing global concern of SSA's resistance towards FP based on cultural perspective and religious teachings which have become the norms in the societies (47). For example, a qualitative study conducted in Nigeria in 2021 reported that many still perceive God as the one who should determine the timing and number of their children (48). In Nigeria, the highest percentage of demand satisfied (36.7%) in my analysis shows the extent of violation of women's rights to freely decide on when and how many children they want to have. A study with four African countries using DHS data found strong correlation of the level of empowerment of women and the use of modern FP in all the countries (49). The modern FP method transition from oral pills to injectables as the mostly used method in my analysis confirms the finding that there is a widespread use of injectables in SSA and it is the most used method of FP (50). This can be associated to WHO and USAID in 2009 empowering CHWs in SSA in administering depot-medroxyprogesterone acetate (DMPA) injection locally to supplement the health facility-based administration of progestin-only injectables by nurses or doctors (51).

The women in the 1971-75 birth cohort though mostly lived in rural residence, they were mostly working as from 28-32 and older. As expected, when they were at their 15-19 years, the percentage currently working was low. This suggests that many of the women in my study (28-32 years and older) have some financial independence to purchase contraceptives if they do not want to get pregnant. However, the 37.5% of the women at their 15-19 years that were married or cohabiting and 71.8% of them not currently working could result to financial dependence on their partners and less negotiation power to choose FP. Additionally, the mean number of children birthed at the end of women's reproductive life being 6 shows the poor use of FP among the women in my study. Even though, there were more than 60% of them educated with primary, secondary or higher education, the supply of FP products among others could have limited their access to FP.

As the women grew older the change in their mCPR, need for FP and demand satisfied by modern methods followed the same trend. These percentages increased when women were at their 15-19 years and peaked when they were at their 33-37 years and 38-42 years, after which the percentages dropped when women were at their 43-47 years. This corresponds with the findings from Yameen et al, in Pakistan, who documented that women had higher odds to use FP when they are 35 years or younger compared to older than 35 years (52). Contributing to the increase in all the mCPR, and demand satisfied by modern methods over the years in addition to the NPP are INGOs because they have been at the forefront of several SRH programs in Nigeria. Some INGOs that have had long-term programs are Planned Parenthood Federation of Nigeria (PPFN), and more recently “Every Woman, every child”, of which Nigeria been a partner country increased its annual commitment from \$3 million yearly in 2010 to \$8.35 million yearly in 2017 (53). Others include USAID Global Health Supply Chain Program- Procurement and Supply Management (GHSC-PSM), Development partners like Department of International Development (DFID).

5.1 Modern FP method use among all women (mCPR)

The highest percentage of mCPR among all women in the 1971-75 birth cohort, 13.8% is almost similar with the mCPR of 12% among married WRA in the DHS 2018, but it is almost half the mCPR of Africa in 2017 (27%) and even much lower than the global mCPR in 2019 (44%). This means for every three WRA using contraceptive globally, two will be using modern contraceptive in Africa while only one will be using modern contraceptive in Nigeria. The advent of the Nigeria’s foremost NPP which aimed at reducing fertility rate from about six to four children per women resulted into an increased campaign for modern FP. However, several women’s local associations opposed the policy because of the neglect of other aspects of women’s reproductive health and inadequate access to the 1986-launched free Primary health care (54). The unacceptability of this policy contributed to poor use of contraceptives despite being available hence the women in our analysis by the time of this policy, at 15-19 years had a very low mCPR of 1.9%. Furthermore, being adolescents contributed to this very low mCPR as stigmatization affects access of adolescents in SSA to modern FP (55). Women aging to their 28-32 years in 2008, when the NPP has evolved with a paradigm shift from a population-control approach to a human-rights approach, expectedly had a five-fold increase in their mCPR compared to when women were at their 15-19 years in 1990.

The creation of the FP Blueprint strategy in 2013 coupled with the revised NPP still in place (till 2015) played a big role in the women’s mCPR being highest when women were at their 33-37 and 38-42 years (overlapping 95% CIs). Additionally, women at these age groups (with the highest mCPR) had the highest proportion of higher education. This corresponds with Bongaarts and Hardee’s regression

analysis of mCPR trends in SSA that found education to be significant in the outcome of mCPR (40). Had the revised NPP reached its target by the end of 2015, mCPR should have been 30.2% rather than 9.8% (32). The graph in figure 3 was set at the maximum point of 35% because 36% was the highest mCPR we have ever aimed as a nation but we are yet to achieve.

5.2 Need for FP

The need for FP provides an estimation of the percentage of women who need FP among all women because not every woman in her reproductive age has a need for FP. Not all non-users of modern FP desire to get pregnant, some are not using modern FP because they cannot get pregnant through normal reproductive process. The need for FP was lowest when women were at their 15-19 years which could either be because they want to get pregnant or because they are not yet sexually active, or they could be ignorant of their SRH rights. Regarding sexual activity, a study done in five SSA in 2019 shows that 43.5 % of girls, 15-19 years are sexually active (56). While in DHS, it is reported that 35.4% of women have been sexually active before 18 years (DHS 2018). 30.5% of girls at 15-19 years know about modern FP while 23.0% know a source for modern FP method (DHS 2018). With these, it is likely most of the women at their 15-19 were either not sexually active or they were ignorant about SRH rights and FP. The need for FP continued to increase as women aged with the highest percentage being among women at their 33-37 years in 2008 which can be associated to the effect of the revised NPP in Nigeria at this time. The overlap of the 95% intervals, as the women at their 33-37 aged to women at their 43-47 years shows that there has not been any significant increase in the need for FP during this period.

5.3 Demand satisfied

From the result of my analysis, the demand satisfied by modern methods starting off at 13.3% for the women at their 15-19 years means among the 14.6% who needed modern FP in this age-group, only 1 in 8 had need for FP met (demand satisfied) while the majority 85.4% had an unmet need. Contrasting this value of demand satisfied (13.3%) with the mCPR of the women within this age group at 1.9%, there is an underestimation of the users of modern FP, looking at the mCPR's value alone. This underestimated mCPR of 1.9% assumed all women of reproductive age 15-19 years would use modern FP, which is not the case for women not in need of modern FP. These values confirms demand satisfied as a more specific indicator than mCPR. Based on its specificity, demand satisfied for modern method was adopted by the SDG to be the indicator of the 2030 SDG 3.7 Demand satisfied being a percentage among those in need for FP also highlights the rights of women in choosing to use modern FP or not, hence the SDG complementary target of "universal access to sexual and reproductive health rights" (SDG 5.6). Looking at the 95% CIs, there seems to be an overlap between among all the age groups

apart from the 15-19 years old. This shows that there is no statistical difference between these values, hence the demand satisfaction by modern methods has nonetheless remained the same after the double-fold increase that was experienced as women aged from 15-19 years. The percentage was highest though when women were at their 38-42 years in 2013. Recall that 2013 was the year of the double impact of the revised NPP and the FP blueprint in scaling up access to modern FP in Nigeria.

The demand satisfied by modern methods remained low throughout the lifetime of the women, the highest point being 36.7% is much lower than the benchmark percentage of 75% set by the United Nations. This corresponds with a multilevel analysis of DHSs of high-fertile SSA where the demand satisfied by modern methods stood at 39.5% (20). This low percentage in Nigeria shows the inadequacies within the supply side of contraceptives which can be associated with how contraceptives are procured and distributed. Several hiccups such as problems at procuring the products, poor data management which is still manual reporting in many centers, persistence of weak health inadequate staff, poor storage and poor transportation leads to stock out of products and distribution delay across the country (57,58). Between 2018 and 2019, as much as 41% stock out of contraceptives was reported by the Nigeria Health Logistics Management Information System (58). The unavailability of the free contraceptives made demand satisfied by modern methods skewed to the women with higher education, women currently working and consequently with higher income to purchase contraceptives which is consistent with the women in our study as they became older.

5.4 Unmet need

The percentage of women with unmet need from our analysis declined as the women aged with the same rate as the demand satisfied increased since both indicators add up to a 100%. The significant difference between the unmet need of the women at their 15-19 years (86.7%) and the unmet need when the women were at their 28-32 years (70.7%) might be linked to the neglect of girls at 15-19 years in Nigeria. Globally, there is a neglect of the SRH needs of adolescents over the years despite its unfavorable consequences of unsafe abortions, high rates of HIV and STIs. In a WHO's 2020 report, about 16 million girls between 15-19 years become pregnant and in LMICs, about 33% of these pregnancies are unintended and consequently about a third of these pregnancies result in unsafe abortions (55). Women at this age in Nigeria face higher risk of marriages initiated by their parents to much older male partners for religious and economic reasons irrespective of the decision of the girls, which might result in the violation of their SRH rights in using modern FP (59). The unexpected increase in unmet need of women at their 43-47 years can be associated to the increasing insecurity level in Northern Nigeria resulting from the insurgence of armed bandits from 2015 till date. This has further weakened the poorly-governed health system in Nigeria for example in Zamfara state, banditry

activities resulted in 23 out of 41 health care centers closed as many residents fled the state to other parts of the country seeking refuge (60).

5.5 Method mix

Having understood the trend of the indicators of FP analyzed in this thesis, I will examine the trend of the method mix within the 1971-75 birth cohort as they age through their reproductive years.

As expected the women in our analysis at their 15-19 years all used contraceptive for spacing. The use of injectables as the most prevalent method for spacing when the women were 38-42 years questions their actual intention to space because injectable being a LARC is used for limiting. From the evidence that men want more children than women, the partners of these women might have wanted more children while the women do not want any more children hence they hid their real intention of limiting and answered the question as though they were spacing(48). Using to space rather than using to limit also violates women's SRH right. Even though DHS accounted the use of injectables as a LARC, some other sources of evidence contrastingly classified it as a SAM (29,61). This could be because the widely used DMPA with one year of contraceptive efficacy needs to be taken every 3 months (62). Women also can only get pregnant after an average of 5 months from the last injection, hence it can be more appropriate for spacing in some contexts.

Interestingly, injectables was the most prevalent method for limiting all through the reproductive years of the women. This might have been because of the UK government funded health program: Maternal, Newborn, and Child Health Program from 2004 -2019 (MNCH) in Nigeria. The UK's DFID collaborated with FGoN to provide at no cost, a long-acting contraceptive injection (DMPA-SC / Sayana Press) while training about 2,000 CHWs through 42 master classes on how to use and teach women in remote locations (63). Sayana Press which is a subcutaneous injection can be self-administered and with its shorter needle compared to regular injections, it gives little or no pain. This program across six northern states in Nigeria can be a good example of a rights-based FP approach because women were empowered (cost-free and self-administered FP method) to make independent choices regarding their SRH. At the end of 2019, the FP target of MNCH was the only one that was reached and surpassed among all the targets of the program regarding maternal and child health as more than 1.5 million women were provided modern FP. After the roll up of the program, the UK government continued the supply of Sayana Press to FmoH in Nigeria however it was at some cost. Aggregating the users of modern FP by their intention to either space or limit, shows that the more children women have as they age, the more they change from using modern FP for spacing to using for limiting.

5.6 Strengths and limitations of this study

This is a unique analysis made possible with a sequence of five DHS surveys in Nigeria which is sufficiently powered to produce estimates for 5-year age groups of women. It allowed me to track a synthetic cohort (repeat cross-sectional samples) of women born in 1971-1975 through their reproductive life-course, starting at age 15-19 years and ending at age 43-47 years. Had this same cohort was followed over a life-course, it would have been much more expensive and cohorts also face loss to follow up and deaths sometimes. Additionally, in handling the DHS datasets, I ensured the older DHSs which missed some variables were adjusted for so that all variables are similar across the 5 DHSs. I also controlled for the sampling design in calculating my proportion and 95% CIs and considered the confidence intervals in interpreting my results. I ensured missing data were excluded before calculating the percentages and 95% CIs. However, this analysis also has limitations. I focus here on the three most important.

First, not following up the same women throughout the 28-year period of my analysis. This limitation arose because of the study design of DHS. This survey is done at every five years and each year follows a cross-sectional design rather than a cohort, hence the sampling design is such that ensures maximum randomness. To compensate for this limitation, I looked at the distribution of religion – assuming this changes very little from age 15-19 to age 43-47, and you found that the distribution of religion in the 5 surveys was identical (confidence intervals overlapped). So you are reasonably confident that the repeat sampling is providing you with a representative synthetic cohort and results which can be reliable. It is impossible to estimate the impact of this limitation on my result.

Secondly, the timing of the available surveys is not fully ideal for my research objective. This limitation is due to the unavailability of DHS data in Nigeria between 1990 and 2003. I compensated for this limitation by using available data, and excluded the age group 20-27 years that was not represented in my analysis. The inclusion of the age groups would have had an impact on the interpretation of my result and not on the result itself for example, the consistently huge difference between values when women were 15-19 and when they were 28-32.

Lastly, the validity of correct reporting cannot be assessed. This limitation is from the data collection process which is done using questionnaires and the validity of these responses based on social desirability cannot be ascertained especially because the women themselves are reporting these sensitive issues of use of FP, the method they are using and the intention of use. For example, the wide 95% CIs of the women at their 28-32 years in the figure 3 show some inaccuracies in the estimate. This limitation is compensated for to a large extent because questions were asked the women within the

research ethics of confidentiality. Social desirability bias leading to inaccurate responses would underestimate the percentages because women using modern FP may report otherwise as FP is still not socially fully accepted in Nigeria.

CHAPTER SIX: CONCLUSION and RECOMMENDATIONS

6.1 Conclusion

The demand satisfied by modern methods of contraceptives among WRA in Nigeria needs to be scaled up and this requires an increased political will towards empowering women on their Sexual and Reproductive rights at every reproductive year age-group. Empowering women facilitates their demand for FP. When women know the various modern FP methods and where to acquire the services, they can make informed choice on using modern FP. This increase in demand in turn would positively affects the supply of the various FP methods thus FP policies should be designed to empower women.

6.2 Policy Recommendations

To FGoN: FP should be a women empowerment strategy as much as it is population control strategy, hence in addition to NPP, policies focused on women empowerment should be formulated. For example policies that ensures the patriarchal system is diffused so that women can have more autonomy in decision making should be formulated. Policies that encourage the female child education and more employment opportunities for women should be formulated.

To Ministry of Education: Policy that encourage sex education as a part of the education curriculum should be formulated. This education should emphasize on their SRH rights while connecting the young people with FP sources around their community.

6.3 Implications for future research

- More research should be done globally and across different regions focusing on estimating only the women in need for FP as this indicator is neglected in accessing modern FP use.
- FP Policy implementation research to review the role of FGoN and partner organizations locally and internationally while assessing the governance and accountability structure within the implementation design of all FP policies in Nigeria.
- A research project involving a massive nationwide campaign for FP and health education on the various modern FP methods using every media outlet such as print media, mass media and social media platforms in Nigeria. This is because of the low percentage of the need for FP based on my findings.
- Qualitative research among girls in senior secondary schools in Nigeria to know the extent of the SRH rights that they are aware of and how the girls can protect these rights.
- Research into FP programs in Nigeria and how they can be more effective in scaling up demand satisfied by modern methods not only as a population control strategy but as a women empowerment strategy.

- Finally, I would recommend more studies to be designed using the synthetic cohort approach in monitoring trends, especially when working with large, nationally representative data like the DHS.

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CHAPTER EIGHT: ANNEXES

Annex 1: Definition of modern methods

Modern methods	Definition	Source
Female and male condoms	<p>Male condom: Sheath or covering that fit over a man’s erected penis. Also protects against sexually transmitted infections, including HIV.</p> <p>Female condom: forms a barrier to prevent sperm and egg from meeting</p>	<p>United Nations</p> <p>WHO</p>
Contraceptive pills	Contains either estrogen and progestogen, or progestogen only. Taken daily, prevents the release of eggs from the ovaries.	United Nations
Injectables	Injected into the muscle or under the skin every 1, 2 or 3 months, depending on product.	United Nations
Implants	Small, flexible rods or capsules placed under the skin of the upper arm; contains either estrogen and progestogen, or progestogen only. Health-care provider must insert and remove; can be used for 3–5 years depending on implant.	United Nations
Intrauterine devices (IUDs)	Small flexible plastic device containing copper sleeves or wire inserted into the uterus. Some devices steadily release small amounts of levonorgestrel each day. Health-care provider must insert and remove; can be used for 3–5 years depending on implant.	United Nations
Male and female sterilization	<p>Female sterilization: Permanent contraception to block or cut the fallopian tubes (also known as tubal ligation).</p> <p>Male sterilization: Permanent contraception to block or cut the vas deferens tubes that carry sperm from the testicles to the penis (also known as vasectomy).</p>	United Nations
Diaphragm	A circular dome made of thin, soft silicone inserted into the vagina before sex. It covers the cervix so sperm cannot get into the womb (uterus) to fertilize an egg.	NHS UK
Foam and jelly	These methods of birth control contain spermicide, a chemical that kills sperm. and they dissolve in the vagina.	Peel Public health

Lactational amenorrhea method (LAM)	A contraceptive method where the mother is <i>informed and supported</i> how to use breastfeeding for contraception. Breastfeeding while <i>not</i> giving supplementary feeds delays the return of fertility and menstrual periods, which is a normal (physiological) protection against pregnancy.	Cochrane
Emergency contraception	Prevents or delays the release of eggs from the ovaries. Pills taken to prevent pregnancy up to 5 days after unprotected sex. For example ulipristal acetate 30mg (UPA), levonorgestrel 1.5mg (LNG), combined oral contraceptive pills.	WHO

Annex 2: Table showing the Modern Contraceptive Prevalence Rate

Key indicators	1990		2003		2008		2013		2018	
	%	95% CI	%	95% CI	%	95% CI	%	95% CI	%	95% CI
Age range	15-19		28-32		33-37		38-42		43-47	
Women	1553		1127		3794		4156		3455	
Current contraceptive use by any modern method (%)	1.9	1.3-2.8	9.4	7.4-11.8	13.8	12.5-15.2	13.7	12.7-15.2	9.7	8.5-11.0

Annex 3: Table showing the Need for FP

Key indicators	1990		2003		2008		2013		2018	
Age range	15-19		28-32		33-37		38-42		43-47	
Women	1553		1127		3794		4156		3455	
	%	95% CI								
Need for FP (%)	14.6	12.2-17.3	33.2	29.0-37.7	41.5	39.6-43.3	37.2	35.3-39.2	32.8	30.4-35.3

Annex 4: Table showing the Modern contraceptive users for spacing and limiting

Key indicators	1990		2003		2008		2013		2018	
Age range	15-19		28-32		33-37		38-42		43-47	
Women	37		109		479		583		337	
	%	95% CI	%	95% CI	%	95% CI	%	95% CI	%	95% CI
Users for spacing	100.0		76.4	72.4-80.1	52.6	48.0-57.1	28.2	24.2-32.7	9.7	6.9-13.6
Users for limiting	0.00		23.6	19.9-27.6	47.4	42.9-52.0	71.8	67.3-75.8	90.3	86.4-93.1

Annex 5: Table showing the The Unmet need and demand satisfied by modern methods

Key indicators	1990		2003		2008		2013		2018	
Age range	15-19		28-32		33-37		38-42		43-47	
Women	37		109		479		583		337	
	%	95% CI								
(Unmet) Need for FP (%)	13.3	9.2-19.0	28.3	23.0-34.0	33.4	30.7-36.0	36.7	33.6-40.0	29.5	25.8-33.0
Demand satisfied by modern methods (%)	86.7	81.3-91.0	71.7	65.7-77.0	66.6	63.9-69.0	63.3	60.1-66.0	70.5	66.6-74.0